

Intercultural Mediation Training and the Training Process of Common Sense Leaders by the Leadership of Universities Communication and Artistic Campaigns

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Abstract—It is quite essential to form dialogue mechanisms and dialogue channels to solve intercultural communication issues. Therefore, every country should develop a intercultural education project which aims to resolve international communication issues. For proper mediation training, the first step is to reach an agreement on the actors to run the project. The strongest mediation mechanisms in the world should be analyzed and initiated within the educational policies. A communication-based mediation model should be developed for international mediation training. Mediators can use their convincing communication skills as a part of this model. At the first, fundamental stages of the mediation training should be specified within the scope of the model. Another important topic at this point is common sense and peace leaders to act as an ombudsman in this process. Especially for solving some social issues and conflicts, common sense leaders acting as an ombudsman would lead to effective communication. In mediation training that is run by universities and non-governmental organizations, another phase is to focus on conducting the meetings. In intercultural mediation training, one of the most critical topics is to conduct the meeting traffic and performing a shuttle diplomacy. Meeting traffic is where the mediator organizes meetings with the parties with initiative powers, in order to contribute to the solution of the issue, and schedule these meetings. In this notice titled “ Intercultural mediation training and the training process of common sense leaders by the leadership of universities communication and artistic campaigns”, communication models and strategies about this topic will be constructed and an intercultural art activities and perspectives will be presented.

Keywords—Intercultural communication, mediation education, common sense leaders, artistic sensitivity

I. INTRODUCTION

TO settle the disputes which international communities go through and to remove the obstacles on the way of proper intercultural communication, having common sense is one of the most important communicational qualities. Having common sense is the key to find a common point for both parties and to come up with a reasonable solution when settling an intercultural dispute. Communication pioneers are needed to create a common sense climate for maintaining the intercultural peace by helping different cultures feel mutual understanding, tolerance, goodwill and the need for a constructive approach. “Common Sense Leaders” are the people who will lead this mission for maintaining international peace and building an intercultural consensus.

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In an institutional structure created as a Non-Governmental United Nations including various universities from all around the world, training international common sense leaders and giving the initiative to universities will help the course of the process. This process is particularly based on training and educating the potential Common Sense leaders who are university students throughout their university lives, and will contribute to the intercultural peace culture by dynamizing the common sense leaders in diplomacy. Public relations and artistic campaigns run by universities play a large part in common sense leaders training. In order to appeal to public conscious and bring the public to a reasonable agreement via common sense leaders when settling disputes, the sensibility aspect of artistic campaigns and the power to mold a public opinion of public relations campaigns have a key role.

II. EFFECTIVE MEDIATION MECHANISMS IN INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION

It is quite essential to form dialogue mechanisms and dialogue channels to solve intercultural communication issues. Therefore, every country should develop a intercultural education project which aims to resolve international communication issues. For proper mediation training, the first step is to reach an agreement on the actors to run the project. The strongest mediation mechanisms in the world should be analyzed and initiated within the educational policies. A communication-based mediation model should be developed for international mediation training. Mediators can use their convincing communication skills as a part of this model. “Probably the most common question raised about mediation(both domestic and international)is how a party should go about identifying a suitable mediator. We would rephrase that as two slightly different questions:(1)how does one go about locating candidates for a mediator role,and(2)how does one select a mediator who is appropriate for the dispute?” [1]. At the first, fundamental stages of the mediation training should be specified within the scope of the model.

A. Mediation Training in Universities

Universities hold most of the responsibility on planting the mediation mechanism in intercultural education. Mediation trainings that universities organize should also involve social education and awareness-raising campaigns. One of themes for these campaigns is the sharing of social sensitivity and sensitive areas of each society and culture. One of the most important building blocks of mediation training is to form a sensitivite mechanism. “Thus cultural mediators are not perceived as a neutral third side but rather are expected to operate for the sake of social justice in the community and for the sake of cultural sensitivity). [2].

For the mediators who are responsible for creating a mutual and agreeable story between the parties, it would be a good example to pioneer a public relations and social education campaign that is run by Ege University, Turkey, with the motto of ; "Let's Feel Our Mutual Grievs With Our Mutual Consciences". With a campaign that 1 million university student will participate that takes place in Hiroshima Peace Memorial Park, Japan, will play an important role on raising awareness about the subject. This park was dedicated to Hiroshima, the first city in the world that went through a nuclear attack in 1949, and was designed by Japanese architect Kenzo Tange, in order to reprobate the attack and become a symbol against nuclear armament, 4 years after the nuclear bomb attack on Hiroshima.

The campaign will start with the ringing of the peace bell located in the park by 1000 university rectors from around the world and is an excellent example of intercultural communication, making a social call with the motto "Share The Bells of Your Consciences with the Songs of Peace". 100.000 students from universities around the world and 1000 rectors will participate in the activity and their presence will empower the campaign. In an intercultural education project starting with an effective campaign, the first task to do is to define the mutual grief. Here, the mutual grief is a common outcry and confrontation, engaged by an event that caused deep pains, migration and many deaths in the history of a nation. In intercultural education, universities should emphasize on respecting the mutual grief and confronting it. Therefore, historians chosen from each country should write about the mutual grief.

It is a very important step for intercultural education projects to call an assembly of historians from every country, in order to discuss and review the subject and declare the agreed ideas and grief to the public. As a result of the assembly, griefs that represent the mutual sensitivity and awareness of the society should be transformed into an intercultural education project. For that matter the , primary steps are to involve cultural ambassadors, historians, university students and academics of other countries in the project and maintain an intercultural platform. Universities should pioneer, and consider these types of projects as a mission leading to social contribution. To build and develop an effective dialogue mechanism requires the recognition of mutual briefs and acknowledging them. When universities take academical initiatives and make objective researches about the subject, reliability and credibility of the project will be empowered. Basic foundation of the education should be datas, documents and archives. Therefore, in an intercultural education project, it is necessary to clearly identify the basic foundations, to structure these foundations with powerful communication tools and techniques, and create a common story about recognition and understanding of the mutual grief. "Coordinators and mediators can(1)equally distribute opportunities of participation among the interlocutors, and (2)enhance mutual sensitivity among the interlocutors. Affective formulations, suggestive narratives and unconditional appreciations are important for this function as forms of coordinator's and mediator's deliberate self-positioning, i.e. self- disclosure.

Moreover, coordination and mediation may also be enhanced through simpler supporting actions, such as promotional questions, continuers, end echoes showing the mediator's and coordinator's reflecting attitude" [3]. These strong foundations and emphases will also be a meaningful and an legitimate expression of sensibility. For an intercultural education project, mediation pioneers must be found and valued. To both creating a dialogue mechanism and resolving the conflicts, mediation pioneers and common sense leaders of each culture should be determined.

II. INTERCULTURAL MEDIATION TRAINING AND COMMON SENSE LEADERS

Common sense leaders are the people who will take the essential initiatives for the dialogue education of societies. One of the most important building blocks of international peace education is to avoid intercultural violence and make the conscience and common sense dominant within the societies. "Peace education means learning to trust in the common sense that people have and non-acceptance of old, fixed beliefs such as security, defence and heroism." [4]. 30 characteristic qualities that common sense leaders should have for intercultural training can be summarized like this :

- Common sense leaders are the leaders that have the courage to expose and confront some social truths to the public of which everybody else struggles to.
- Common sense leaders are the respected pioneers of a social movement that is identified with their names and identities
- Common sense leaders are the people who contribute to the social peace and fight for it.
- Common sense leaders are the people whose social calls will affect masses and get responses.
- Common sense leaders are the people who created peaceful values identified with their names.
- Common sense leaders possess a road map, a formula and a unique idea to solve problems.
- Common sense leaders are the people that opened dialogue channels more than once and built their courses on peace.
- Common sense leaders are the people who possess the terminology of peace and have mastered it.
- Common sense leaders are the people who can use the shuttle diplomacy among the society.
- Common sense leaders are the people who possess the communication skills for reaching a mutual understanding in the society.
- Common sense leaders are the people who can take initiatives on mediating and conflict management.
- Common sense leaders are the people whom the society wishes to take initiative.
- Common sense leaders can define the most sensible points of the society and turn these sensibilities into a mutual understanding
- Common sense leaders represent the social common sense with the model and road map they have drawn. They are the people who can define the starting point of social common sense.

- Common sense leaders are the people whose life stories are identified with the values they defend.
- Common sense leaders are the people who can prevent the social prejudices from overcoming the social griefs and make the society act on their advices about fighting the prejudices.
- Common sense leaders are the people who can speak out the social griefs on legitimate platforms, and lead the people to legitimate fights in order to reminisce and prevent these griefs.
- Common sense leaders are the people who can properly express the similar griefs of societies to public and build common sense symbols that represent the mutual griefs of humanity.
- Common sense leaders are the people who can use intercultural communication codes for mutual understanding of different griefs of different cultures, and adopt basic principles.
- Common sense leaders are the people who are considered as the legitimate reference in both their cultural environments and international platforms
- Common sense leaders are the people who can properly express the cultural differences to the society and use these cultural differences to form a climate of understanding in order to reach meaningful goals.
- Common sense leaders possess the resolution initiative that is accepted by governmental agencies and institutions.
- Common sense leaders are the people who recognize the concerns, worries and dellusions about the future and make them noticed. They are the ones who contribute to build the future on faith and trust.
- Common sense leaders are the people who identify the eigenvalues and moral values of a culture with the dialogue mechanism and create a mutually agreed peace formula of these values.
- Common sense leaders are the people who introduce “the other” to the society and defend “the other”’s right to live. They strongly defend “the other”’s social struggle of existence.
- Common sense leaders are the people who defend the victim in both their countries and around the world, and make humanity recognize the victims that were created within the system.
- Common sense leaders are the people who create the tools that make the society to confront themselves, activate the dynamics and mirror the society.
- Common sense leaders are the people who can also create a leadership mechanism. They are the people who can lead the platforms that gather the people with common sense together, and guide the succeeding leaders .
- Common sense leaders are the people who can create the proper symbols that represent the intercultural consensus and common sense and turn these symbols into common symbols that spread rapidly within various communication platforms.
- Common sense leaders are the people who build their persuasive skills on righteous, objective knowledge, a transparent frame, accountable communication activities

and respectable principles, and most important of them all they are the people who arouse respect.

In order to create a solid mediation mechanism in intercultural communication, first of all, right common sense leaders should be determined, and every culture should raise their own common sense leaders. A solid philosophy which can draw the communication frame with high efficiency and build sensitivity areas within a dialogue mechanism must be founded .

III. THE TRAINING PROCESS OF COMMON SENSE LEADERS

One of the most important steps when developing a mediation and dialogue mechanism is the training process of common sense leaders and effective management of this process. .”Effective peace education needs to be based on an adequate understanding of what peace is. This notion of peace education, understood as involving nondominant relations between different cultures, requires major academic research work towards the construction of concept of peace”. [5]. In this regard, an intercultural sensibility platform that consists of universities and non-governmental organizations organized in a very wide consensus is suggested. The first step of the planned sensibility mechanism is to form a “Non-Governmental United Nations”. This non-governmental united nations organization should be led by universities and have a representative from all countries, and should be located in Hiroshima to symbolize the mutual grief, and be voluntary. For the central of this platform, founded by universities and non-governmental organizations for the resolution of intercultural issues and to develop an efficient mediation and dialogue mechanism, Hiroshima University is recommended.

In this platform, it should be aimed to train thousands of common sense leaders a year. In this regard, an intercultural training model should be developed. Firstly, the main issues and fields to be mediated should be determined. The fields that require professional and key mediators should be determined and concentrate on the related training projects and topics. Critically significant starting points when determining the intercultural training topics can be listed as such : Perception of danger of the people of the world should be determined and intercultural education projects should be developed according to these perceptions : Humanity’s worst fears and concerns towards the future should be determined and communication and training projects should be developed to prevent these concerns from causing an intercultural communication conflict. Determining what the humanity sees as a threat and managing this perception properly is one of the fundamentals of an intercultural training that focuses on developing a mediation mechanism. Therefore, each university participating in the Non-Governmental United Nations should make large scaled researches and determine the biggest intercultural threat perception in their countries. In this regard, mediators bear a great responsibility. “Broadly speaking, there are number of ways of managing international conflicts. Four different approaches to conflict management may be identified.

These are (1) threats, use of force and competence, (2) deterrence, (3) adjudication, and (4) accommodation (e.g., negotiation and mediation). [6].

Therefore, through an efficient mediation mechanism, intercultural perception management should be analyzed.

The most important step for the intercultural training project through mediation is to develop communication projects to remove these perceptions of threat. One of the biggest conflicts for intercultural communication is different cultures seeing each other as a threat. This is the starting point of the mediation training. "With a thorough review of the overall process of how stereotype threat is designed and measured, questions arise. The measurement of the methodology and the resulting factors is through a confirmed decrease in performance on a selected achievement measure. The formative process of targeting a widely known stereotype, determining (or not) a priming method to invoke stereotype threat, the measurement procedures, and potential use of surveys as mediators, all performed in a laboratory setting" [7]. Therefore, training projects that are based on "Different cultures living together in harmony" must be prepared. Training campaigns organized by universities for this regard, will help to raise future mediators. For instance, about Israel-Palestine crisis, a campaign run by universities may produce mediators much more efficiently than diplomacy. A peace project to be conducted by Al Kuds University, Palestine Science and Technology Academy, Ramallah Birzeit University of 12 universities in Palestine and Jerusalem Hebrew University, Haifa Technical Institute of 7 universities in Israel, can be one of the most powerful and vivid examples of mediation in intercultural communication.

It would be a very important step for intercultural training and peace project to organize shared activities by announcing an immune area among these 19 universities within the "Non-Governmental United Nations" project. This project can be supported by the United Nations Secretary General and will have a facilitating effect on the peace talks. The main topics of the intercultural training project to be developed between Israel and Palestine can be: the art of living together, respecting mutual griefs, meeting at common humanistic values, fighting the intercultural violence. For instance, universities in both countries can abandon the language of violence that exploits the future based concerns and fears and build a mutual initiative for the domination of the language of peace which would be the foundation of the intercultural training.

IV. TRAINING OF PEACE LITERATURE

Presenting the students the sample of the literature that causes conflicts and tension between two nations and creating a mutual peace literature and reshaping the educational format, is one of the most strategic sections of mediation training. This type of an education would be one of the foundations of the idea of a "Peace Literature" and will teach the society how to live together with mutual respect. This education project should be planned as a communication campaign and turned into a peace project. This project should also gain the power of molding a public opinion. Therefore, a campus site that is located in a shared area can be announced as "the immune area" and accepted as the official starting point of a peace project.

The declaration that was announced by 19 universities in two countries with the decision of the senate is at the same time evaluated as the manifest of this intercultural educational.

"We as the rectors of 19 universities in Israel and Palestine have signed an agreement on a mutual peace education project in order to make an academical contribution to tolerance and dialogue channels, and to serve culture of peace, as well as providing with a region cleared of violence. With this project we aim to create peace ambassadors and have the leaders of common sense in order to make these 2 societies adopt the motto of living together and to make symbolic steps about this issue and reach ultimate targets. In this manner, to improve the educational projects; in Palestine Ramallah Birzeit University and in Jerusalem Hebrew University campuses are being announced as the campus areas away from every type of violence and peace education project is being started."

In such a peace education project, one of the most important contribution that universities can make is to make up a peace literature and peace literature education. In intercultural communication, in societies that experience conflicts and big difficulties, one of the main communication blocks is a kind of conflict literature that is provoking and based on violence. So as to change this literature and constitute a peace literature based on peace and away from violence, to give an education for the benefit of university students and constitution of the outline of this peace language, and at the end of this education, during the negotiations organized for living together and mutual understanding, educate them about what kind of a communication language they will use is one of the greatest talents that the future mediators are to earn. The main topics of the peace literature can be listed as follows:

- How is the provocative discourse developed. What are the words based on provocation in communication and what kind of initiative is needed to eliminate them?
- What expressions are needed to use during the negotiations in order to provide and focus on peace? What kind of verbal expression types have the characteristics to remind peace?
- What are the words including the most prejudicial expressions in intercultural communication in? What kind of cooperation can be made in terms of less usage of these words and blocking the process of solution?
- What type of communication language should be used to criticize and bring up the violence that is caused by the opposition during the peace talks? Through which expressions should the violence be mentioned?
- How should the common sense language be activated and to create a common conscience? How is common sense depicted in the form of verbal communication?
- Which adjectives are correct to use to express mutual complaints and concerns?
- How to set up the verbal statements and types of expressions to express mutual demands regarding peace? What kind of communication language should be used for the demands?
- What are the key phrases to communicate the steps determined in case mutual warnings and terms of peace?

aren't met? How are these key phrases used in order to not block the process?

- What are the phrases, adjectives and words that have the uppermost effect on the peace negotiations?
- What are the negative reflections of language used in newsreports? How can the news language be used to foster the peace negotiation?
- Which communication techniques can be used in order to deliver the peace language society and the society understand it? Which phases should occur for the society to adopt the peace language?
- How to benefit from the opinion leaders to make the peace language popular in daily life usage?
What are the outlines of communication and public relation campaigns on this subject?
- What are the concepts that both parties will never argue on and take as great value? What kind of communication language should be used for these values in negotiation?
- What kind of communication language should be used in apology required situations to prevent the abuse of reputation and national pride.
- What are the channels that the language causing conflict and provocation is commonly used and spread quickly?

A fifteen item peace literature education prepared by universities is one of the most important phases of the mediation mechanism. Mediation at the same time, is built on using the correct communication language persuasively in the constitution of a negotiation atmosphere and maintaining its traffic towards peace and agreement. Henceforth, in the problems caused by the lack of intercultural communication, it is a fostering approach to develop an educational project in order to improve the peace language and make it prevalent in the society by universities. One of the most important bases of the universities in the intercultural education projects is to provide the terms of mutual peace conditions of the societies and contribute to the mediation mechanism dedicated to peace. The peace education that take place in the world are generally ranging among 8-12,13-15,16-18,18-25 age groups and aims to increase the values strengthening the peace literature and eliminate the prejudices effecting the process negatively. "Critical Pedagogy and peace education share the concept of agency, which describes the knowledge and ability to act for collective as well as individual betterment. The notion of communication code supports discursive methods of transformation while awareness of habitus facilitates understanding of interaction during conflict communication" [8].

In the context of these fundamentals, during the mediation education run by universities, a map of communication blocks caused by the intercultural differences should be provided and should be examined. On the most important phases of the education to be done about this subject is the usage of symbols to reduce the cultural differences in the solution of disagreement and an educational society about it. The aim here is to create communication codes accepted by all cultures in the world and present common symbols. It is suggested that all the cultural codes taken into consideration by every culture around the world should be demonstrated by the universities through an educational program.

Various topics should be determined and a harmony of intercultural distinctions created. For instance in the mediation education project that is to enforce the communication of European countries with the others in the continent, a mediation education curriculum which is to be applied in all European universities simultaneously integrated to Non-Governmental U.N. should be made.

Within the scope of "Europe-Far East", "Europe-Africa", "Europe-Middle East", "Europe-Latin America" Mediation Training mechanism, organizing intercultural mediation training programs every three months in universities will present an effective mechanism, especially to adapt to the cultural differences. For instance, organizing mediation training programs in every member country of the Non-Governmental United Nations, scheduled as "Europe-Far East" between October and December, in "Europe-Africa" between December and March, in "Europe-Middle East" between March and June, in "Europe-Latin America" between June and September, is a great contribution of universities to intercultural communication. Diplomats, artists, gastronomes, linguists, journalists, communication experts, and authors from different cultures should be invited to these training projects and in order to choose the educators of the program, a protocol should be signed with ministries of culture and recommended names should be invited as trainers. For instance, topics for "Europe-Far East" mediator training program should be as follows;

- Public interest in movies in the Far East and Far Eastern cinema. Projects related to using movies as a communication tool for resolving issues.
- Body language used in the Far Eastern societies. Saluting and handshaking gestures. Social distance areas that Far Eastern societies use in communication.
- Food culture in the Far East.
- Political sociology, current political leaders and political structure in Far Eastern countries.
- Women's place in social life, gender equality and concept of social gender in Far Eastern countries.
- Non-governmental organizations' power to mold a public opinion in the Far East.
- Major political conflicts in the Far East and their backgrounds.
- Far Eastern music and its place in social communication.
- Major griefs in Far Eastern countries and the way they are expressed.
- Cultures that Far Eastern countries have the closest communication outside of the Far East.
- The least known and interested cultures in the Far Eastern society.
- Dressing styles and clothes in the Far Eastern society. The concept of fashion.
- The most effective philosophical movements in the Far Eastern society.
- An analysis on the Far Eastern media and the effect of the media on daily life and political life.
- Contemporary writers of the Far East and their relations with the society.
- Far Eastern literature and its effect on the society.

- Social media and its power to mold a public opinion in the Far East.
- Far East and democracy. How democratic mechanisms work in Far Eastern societies?
- Comparison of the foreign policies in Far Eastern countries.
- The keys to have an interpersonal communication with a Far Eastern person.
- Perception of Europe from a Far Eastern perspective.
- Major conflicts of the Far Eastern countries among themselves.
- Major problems of Far Eastern countries with the countries in other geographies.
- Common sense leaders of opinion leaders of the Far East.
- The effect of Buddhism in Far Eastern societies and their perception of the other 3 major religions.
- Far eastern martial arts and their effects on the society.
- Population structure, distribution of the population in the far east and cultural characteristics of the young generations.
- Personal communication tools the Far Eastern societies use to express themselves.
- Education percentage in the Far East. Universities and their significance for the society. Science politics.
- Far Eastern languages and methods for learning these languages.

A 3 months training of these topics for university students in Europe, will help the mediators to eliminate the obstacles of communications caused by cultural differences and will improve their sensibility. These 3 month trainings can be completed within a certificate program and will adapt the mediators into the social life. Mediators should learn about different cultures. and most importantly recognize the sensibilities of them.

V. INTERCULTURAL COMMON SENSE MODEL AND ARTISTIC EVENTS

When training common sense leaders, artistic events, artists and training these potential leaders through art play an important part. The reason that artistic activities and artistic designs play an important role when training common sense leaders is the power of the art and the artist to mold a public opinion to sensibility aspect. For the famous German artist Rudolf Arnheim "Creative activities are the most effective way of training visual sensitivity, but looking attentively at works of art will also eventually lead to apprehension of their expressive qualities". [9]. Arnheim also emphasizes the importance of colors for sensitivity: "The Hering Theory of color vision calls for sensitivity to six basic colors: black and white, blue and yellow, green and red. Helmholtz, is endorsing the trichromatic theory of Thomas Young, warned against the popular conviction that the basic pure colors, red, yellow, and blue, were the ones naturally best suited for the job" [10]. Therefore, universities should contribute to the training of common sense leaders with artistic campaigns and artistic production, as much as they do with public relations campaigns.

Beginning with painting, movies and musical activities, various fields of arts should be considered in the training process of common sense leaders. "Peace Workshops" is one of the campaigns to recommend on this issue. Universities that are members of the Non-Governmental United Nations have considered certain parts of the university campuses residing in the cities in UNESCO's list of world cultural heritage as "peace workshops" and these workshops can dynamize the feeling of common sense. For instance, in the Middle East, where violence seems to be permanent, Acacus Mountains in Libya are one of the landmarks in UNESCO's list of world's cultural heritage. It would be an important artistic event for training common sense leaders through their expressions against violence by art, by building an art workshop in an area protected by United Nations and built around the mountain.

Common sense leaders trained by universities should learn about the landmarks in UNESCO's cultural heritage list and through Non-Governmental United Nations, should emphasize the sensibility by organizing artistic designs and activities. Artistic point of view and production contributes to settlement of world nations' issues, mutual griefs, ideals and traditional values by developing an intercultural common sense project. For instance, common sense leaders trained by universities should contact with female artists and sculptors in the areas with intense violence in order to conduct mutual projects. Universities in member nations of Non-Governmental United Nations contacting with female artists in violence intensive neighbour countries is a significant artistic contribution to the leadership training. In this context, for instance, an artistic campaign run by Turkish universities, titled "An international call for the most reasonable painting of common sense" is a significant artistic call for common sense leadership. For instance, it would be a very important event for common sense if a Turkish university would invite female artists in countries such as Syria, Iraq and Iran, and encourage these artists to make paintings about common sense followed by artistic discussions. This event is a significant activity for common sense leaders to emphasize the artistic sensitivity on settling the disputes and solving the problems. One of the most important contributions of these activities which picture a perspective with common sense for the society is their power to mold a public opinion. Artist's and art's power to mold a public opinion draws an artistic frame when solving national and international issues.

Therefore, the common sense related aspects of communities should be determined and artistic activities should be supported in accordance to these aspects in order to create sensitive portraits with correct communication policies. "Determining the social sensitivity aspects of international communities" is a starting point for common sense leadership training in universities. In international communities, these sensitivity aspects commonly focus on values, beliefs, traditions and etc. Societies should have a mutual understanding over these subjects and respect each others'. This mutual understanding and respect will develop the sensitivity about the mentioned fine lines. Artists' sensitivity is the perfect device to spread these feelings of understanding and respect to the communities.

Therefore, future common sense leaders should take these artists as role models. In this context, in order to build a strong common sense structure, a concept titled “Reasonable Artists Communication Group” and a training process is recommended. This communication group formed of artists from all countries will contribute effectively to this process as pioneers of common sense.

Settling the disputes through common sense emphasizes on democracy, human rights, consensus, respecting the differences and belief in peace. One of the most important characteristics of people with common sense and common sense leaders is the time they allow for settling the disputes and their ability to manage this process. In our day, especially about settlement of international issues, the most important quality of the mediators who has the privilege of leadership is to manage the time and set the route for the solution. In this process, artists are the individuals who will adapt the society to a solution and make the greatest contribution. The greatest contribution that the artists can make within this process is to form a consensus between the mentioned values. Consensus of the values also will help to save time.

Common sense leaders should have the artistic point of view which will higher the chances of a consensus over this subject. “Both leadership and art are intimately connected with our daily affairs and to living a good life. Nevertheless, common sense can be delivered in different ways. By asking you to think of yourself as an artist and of leadership as your art, we hope we will have given you novel means to consider your enterprise: a new script, as it were, for common sense that may prove especially helpful to you in the office or on the factory floor”. [11]. It’s one of the most important factors for common sense and dialogue process, for “Reasonable Artists Communication Group” to determine the topics for international artists to take initiative about this subject. It also will make it easier for common sense leaders to manage the time for consensus. One of the most important topics that the artists can take initiative about is to blend in the common people for solving the issues, create a sensitive bond with the public and to determine the activities which are based on the people. Therefore, one of the greatest contributions that the artists can make is to lead the people in mentioned activities about destroying the intercultural prejudices.

For instance, one of the most known political tensions recently is the tension between Israel and Turkey over the ship named “Mavi Marmara”. The killings of the Turkish citizens who were taking aid packs to Gaza by the Israeli soldiers has left a deep scar. Several Israeli artists with common sense coming to Turkey by a peace ship and visiting several cities in Turkey is a perfect example of artists influence on citizens. A similar artistic event and sensitivity can be shown about the Cyprus issue. It would be a significant initiative if Northern Cyprus Turkish Republic and Southern Cyprus took it to draw a line that represents the peace and lead the way for the artists of both countries to create the world’s biggest canvas and dedicate it to peace.

The soul of an artist is also the transformation of common sense to canvases, statues, notes and caricatures.

“Without the wisdom of the people, without common sense, there would be no philosophy and no art. But without philosophy there would still be the wisdom of the people, and, in consequence, there would still be art” [12].

Therefore, for the common sense leaders training in universities, the essence of the soul of an artist should be injected into future common sense leaders’ minds. Other important point than the reasonable time management aspect of settling social disputes with common sense is the phase of transforming reasonable values to symbols by artists. This aspect is essential for future common sense leaders to manage the public opinion and maintain communication with strong campaign management. For instance, informing the public about the end of a war or for the war victims to be heard, a simple drawing of a victim child can turn into a huge force of public opinion against the war itself. Beginning with this picture, the battle against violence can be transformed into a strong form of representation which will form the symbols of the common sense. For example, during the civil war in Syria, Beşar Esad the president of Syria, is using violence against his citizens at all ages and genders. It would be an awareness raising event if a picture drawn by a child war victim was published at 100 newspapers without any comments on the same day.

Bringing the future common sense leaders together with the artists in common sense leaders training run by universities will help the trainees to gain the ability to form “common sense symbols”. Especially for intercultural communication, the recognition and spreading of the intercultural symbols for peace and consensus is a very essential phase to go through. It is an artist reflection that peace is represented by the color white. At this point, the step of common sense to be taken by the artists and art is to capture the starting point of communication in the society through the artistic aspect.

The starting point of the communication is to capture the most sensitive point for the public conscious and to share it with the society itself. This point is also the meeting of common sense with masses of citizens. The recent happenings in Mali and Myanmar are 2 different events that the artists should initiate the starting point of the common sense. The vandalism against the mausoleums in Timbuktu, which are on the list of UNESCO world culture heritage, is a very concerning situation.

It would be an initiation for a sensible line to be drawn if a museum of peace was built in Istanbul with the slogan of “Monuments of humanity are untouchable” within a symbolic mausoleum with the participation of all the universities’ deans and artists from the member countries of the Non-Governmental United Nations. The violence and cruelty that the Muslim minority in Arakan, Myanmar is another tragedy that points out to common sense and leadership. It would be a perfect combination of the artists’ initiative and the common sense leadership if a large choir of artists from all 3 major religions would write and sing hymns of peace. It is suggested to organize an international common sense organization in China with the participation of international religious functionaries.

It would be a proper representation of public conscious if this event took place on the Great Wall of China with the slogan of “ We Don’t Put Walls to Stop the Peace, Life to Live, Humanity”.

The power of the art and the artist to unite the societies within the idea of peace is an important emphasis for the training of future common sense leaders in universities. Therefore, the initiative of the artists, production of artistic projects and artistic touch should be considered within the context of utmost importance and fundamentals of common sense leaders training.

A. Artistic Awareness Campaigns for the Common Sense Leaders Training Pioneered by Universities

Artistic awareness model for the training program of common sense leaders builds an effective communication mechanism. One of the most important phases of this is universities starting art camps and artistic training programs. These art camps should also be able to create an artistic leadership and common sense image. For example, the suggestion for Ege University to start an art camp for Egypt who is going through a tough battle for democracy and human rights, is such ;

1. An art camp in Egypt about art philosophy with the participation of leading artists of Egypt

Such an art camp that will be organized with cooperation with the leading universities of Egypt can especially lead the way for the future mediators and common sense leaders about the issues related to Middle East. For instance ; Egypt is one of the most artintensive countries in the Middle East. Especially the drawings on papiruses have played an important role on the art of painting and drawing. “Papyrus is a water plant. It grew in abundance in ancient Egypt along the shores of the Nile. It was harvested and made into paper. It was cut and the pieces were pressed together. The pulp in the papyrus stem acted like glue and held the stems together. When it was dried,papyrus could be made into different sizes for use by scribes. The scribes dipped a stylus into inkwells and wrote on papyrus” [13].In the scope of these art camps, it would be an important artistic contribution to peace if the artists and students participating in the camp drew about peace on papiruses and exhibit them.

Common sense leaders that participate in the camp presenting the papiruses with peace symbols to the country people would accelerate the peace and common sense process run by the future common sense leaders. An art camp and artistic event in Egypt with the slogan of “ Papyrus Is Drawing the World Peace in the Middle East Now” would be a significant contribution to the world peace and the common sense process. In order to make these ideas happen, the essences of the Egyptian art, artistic trends, philosophy and color culture etc. should be learned.

For instance, temples, mausoleums and drawings on the walls have an important place on the Egyptian art. Wall decorations and embroideries are essential to the Egyptian art and it is almost impossible to find an empty wall.

“The technique of buon fresco,which involves dissolving pigments in lime water and painting them onto a freshly plastered wall so that the paints become an integral part of the ground,was first used by egyptians” [14].Therefore, It would be an important campaign contribution the process of common sense leaders training if Turkey’s common sense leader would start a project in cooperation with non-governmental organizations in Egypt, with the slogan of “ Democracy is tearing up the walls with all the colors of humanity” and lead 1000 Egyptian children to brush a color onto an empty wall in order to support the human rights and democracy battle in Egypt.

For instance, the nuclear energy crisis is one of the most important crisis in our day. U.S.A, France, China, England, Russia and Germany, who form the P5+1 group, are currently running the negotiations with Iran on nuclear issues and Turkey has been participating as an observer or hosting the negotiations occasionally. If common sense leaders took the artistic initiative in these negotiations, it would form a consensus point for settling the dispute. With the leadership of Turkey and with the cooperation of the universities in Turkey, starting the peace campaign with the motto of “ Miniature Model for Peace” and supporting the diplomatic efforts is one of the most positive examples of this approach.

The roots of the art of painting goes back to 12 century in Iran. “Miniature painting is an authentic Persian art,which after the Works of Reza Abbasi in the late Safavid period suffered a rapid decline in style and general development mainly due to the popularity of semi westernised styles introduced to the country by foreign educated artists such as Mohammad Zaman”. [15].

Especially the miniatures in the books are one of the most significant symbols of Persian art. Miniature art is one of the national values of Iran and with this information, an artistic production within the concept of miniature art to deliver the Iranian diplomats with the motto “ It’s time to draw the world peace with traditional Iranian miniatures and humanistic values” would emphasize the importance of peace for creating a common sense culture.

Artistic immunity is another important step for the common sense process and artistic awareness model. Artistic immunity is to consider and include the universal validity of art in order to settle international disputes and removing the intercultural communication obstacles. Therefore, it would be an important contribution to the artistic common sense process to determine a common sense leader from each university member of the Non-Governmental United Nations system and to draw a map of consensus. It is an important creative communication strategy to start an artistic campaign based on the dove with an olive branch image which represents peace. It is an important artistic event in which the common sense leader travels around the world to draw a world common sense map, coloring the regions in war with black, regions in peace with white, regions that are about form a peace climate with blue, regions with conflicts and battles with red, regions with tension with gray, regions with peaceful initiatives with green and regions with common sense with yellow.

In the scope of the map of consensus, it would be the unity of artistic production with common sense if 100 artists from 100 different countries drew 100 different colored peace doves based on the colors on the map of consensus and following the slogan of “ Choose Your Own Color So The Peace Dove Can Fly”.

With the leadership of the universities, main titles of the common sense leaders training through art can be summarized as ;

- Each of the common sense leaders should produce artistic works and share those productions within the scope of this project.
- In the conflicted areas around the world, gaps that can be fulfilled through art should be detected.
- Common sense leaders should analyze the artists and art works around the world so that they can learn how these artists and artworks are valuable for maintaining peace and common sense in each of these countries.
- Which artistic activities and events can be effective for world peace and settling disputes should be determined by common sense leaders.
- Art should be involved in the process within the idea of influencing the public conscious and creating an area of awareness, and common sense leaders should possess the perspective of artistic awareness.
- Starting with the idea that art is free to paint and express griefs, mutual griefs of the world should be channelized into the artistic works a common symbol of grief should be created to trigger the public conscious.
- Victimhood caused by the conflicts and disputes around the world should be expressed through artistic symbols and activities, and common sense leaders should be able to create symbols on this subject.
- Symbols that can symbolize the peace, consensus, human rights and intercultural commonpoints the best should be created through artistic designs and common sense leaders should have control over this process.
- Universities should include the common sense process in artistic programs in their departments.
- A cooperation should be made between the pioneers of art and opinion leaders in non-governmental organizations through the unity of universities and non-governmental organizations.

In the process of common sense leadership, it is essential to capture the correct artistic activity and artistic aspect in order to settle the disputes and run the common sense mechanism. It is a very effective communicational skill for a common sense leader to determine the symbols and events that can trigger the public conscious and express the disputes in the best possible way that they can be expressed. For instance, it would be an important step towards the peace if universities built peace museums within their campuses and allow it to public visits in order to run and manage the initiatives and common sense mechanism. The steps to determine the correct artistic activities and events can be summarized as follows ;

- Artistic activities and events should bear a mission and should make the sense of peace in every aspect.

- Artistic events or activities should involve a strong content, artistic design principles and art works that can be transferred to the next generations.
- Artistic activities and events should involve a proper definition of the factor causing the dispute and should enhance the communicative skills of the common sense leaders.
- Artistic activities and events should include symbols for common sense and make people feel the common sense idea through the art.
- Artistic activities and events should unify with the initiative power of the common sense leaders and should use symbols that will lead the society to use initiative when solving problems.
- Artistic activities and events should point out to a starting point for the public conscious when solving international disputes.
- Artistic activities and events should form peace motives that form the basic parameters of common sense in order to trigger the international common sense.
- Components such as color, form, shape, line etc. should be transformed into humanistic touches and forms of common sense.
- Artistic activities and events should have the power to mold a public opinion and should involve the message, design and content to bear this power.
- Artistic activities and events aimed to create a feeling of common sense should gather the pioneer and wise artists who can help to settle disputes.

Wisemen in arts are the opinion leaders who are well-respected in the society through their works and artistic characteristics. It is an important step to involve these artistic wisemen in the process of training the future common sense leaders in universities. Therefore, it is an important attainment to form platforms to bring the wisemen and the future common sense leaders together and reach a mutual consensus.

B. Mechanism of Wisemen in Art and the Concept of Ombudsman

One of the areas that common sense leaders can contribute to international peace or intercultural communication is the Ombudsman mechanism. An Ombudsman is a reliable and well-respected communication pioneer who can be a judge when solving international issues through neutrality. It is an important step for common sense leaders to elect ombudsmen among themselves in order to determine the process. In this subject, forming a “wisemen committee” for art is the first step to ombudsmanship. Determining the pioneer artists in every country through every field of art who are the symbols of peace, democracy, consensus and the struggles for living together and forming a “wisemen in arts” committee is the first step to form an ombudsmanship process. In this process, artists’ awareness should be manifested. It would be a strategical communication planning process to point out the reliable, objective, neutral people, the wisemen of the arts.

Ombudsmen’s choices are very critical when solving the fundamental problems in intercultural communication. One of the most important qualities of an ombudsman is the mastery of the given subject.

Ombudsman is the person who has the utmost knowledge on every aspect of the subject such as legal, historical and sociological. But in addition to this quality, most important characteristic of an ombudsman is the neutrality and the perception of fair. An ombudsman who can communicate fairly and equally with the both parties, come up with objective solutions, manage the communication process perspicuously, focus on to relief for victims and communicate at the best level, will present the ideal path to solve the problems. Especially, wisemen committee of artists should be consulted to find the right ombudsman who has strong communication skills. Wisemen group in arts are the artists who dedicate their awareness to reach a solution for social problems, combine their works and artistic designs in the concept of solution, produce and share artistic symbols within the mind, conscious and common sense triangle, form initiatives that are identified with himself/herself for creating a peace culture and lead social campaigns and lead their followers through these campaigns.

A painting by wise artists can be the best symbol of the cries of a whole society and can be a masterpiece to place that idea into the minds of international communities through an image. Or the notes of another artist can turn into a march that symbolizes a common grief for humanity. Therefore, when solving intercultural social issues, it is a strong emphasis for the artistic wisemen to call out to person or people who can lead to solve those issues. For example, in the negotiations between Israel and Palestine it is a good example that Palestinian and Israeli artist gathering together to call out to people who can make a positive change on this subject. It is a very strong artistic initiative for peace to combine 50 artists from both countries to form an artistic wisemen group and call out to people who can act as an ombudsman in that situation through their social awarenesses.

One of the most important steps to take on this subject is to bring the wise artists and common sense leaders from Israel and Palestine together. An artistic path to follow on the subject brings out the humanistic emotions and values and is essential for forming a common ground. At this point, common sense leaders and wise artists should emphasize on the process to understand the common griefs and to feel the humanistic sensitivities. When people from both parties recognize and share the common griefs, an important step towards the settlement is taken. Common sense leaders and wise artists are the people who combine the griefs in hearts at the point of a reasonable solution. These efforts also form the cultural diplomacy efforts. Intercultural differences are not obstacles for communication, they should be recognized as cultural richness. The main purpose of a consensus map is to reach an intercultural agreement. Intercultural agreement is a very wide agreement that works through the respect and understanding through different cultures with an immunity on the international platform.

VI. CONCLUSION

Creating a "Common sense Leadership" mechanism in the intercultural platform and developing a common sense model when solving the international disputes are the determining factors of intercultural agreement.

Intercultural agreement involves a strong solidarity with the concept of consensus for different cultures for the peace culture of the future. Common sense leaders are the ones to form the parameters of this intercultural unity and solidarity. Combining this process withing the universities and forming a training program will help common sense leaders to be more equipped and educated. Universities pioneering this training through the aspects of diplomacy, governments, non-governmental organizations, opinion leaders, artists and writers and journalists, is a significant academic contribution to international peace. The priorities of this common sense mechanism are to plan the important steps and campaigns to form a common sense platform in order to make these projects an intercultural public conscious matters through artistic campaigns. Common sense leaders' peace projects and peace initiatives for intercultural consensus and cooperation present important attainments.

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